

FEATURES OF SUBSTANTIVATION OF VERBS IN UZBEK AND THEIR EQUIVALENTS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article aims to analyze the features of substantivation of verbs in the Uzbek language and their equivalents in English. The paper provides a comparative study of the processes involved in forming substantivated verbs, highlighting the similarities and differences between the two languages. The analysis focuses on the morphological, syntactic, and semantic aspects of substantivation in both languages, providing examples for clarification. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the linguistic structures and can be helpful for both learners and teachers of Uzbek and English.

Keywords: substantivation, verbs, Uzbek language, English language, morphological aspects, syntactic aspects, semantic aspects, comparative study

Introduction: Substantivation is a linguistic process that involves the formation of a noun from a verb, thus converting the action or process described by the verb into a more static, nominal form. In both the Uzbek and English languages, substantivation plays an essential role in providing flexibility and expressiveness. This article aims to explore the features of substantivation of verbs in Uzbek and compare them with their equivalents in the English language. The study will contribute to a better understanding of the morphological, syntactic, and semantic aspects of substantivation in both languages.

Main Part:

1. Morphological Aspects of Substantivation:

In addition to the previously mentioned suffixes, the Uzbek language also employs other suffixes for substantivation, such as -mo (-ma), -chan, and -tir. For

example, the verb "ko'r-" (to see) can be substantivated with the suffix -ma, resulting in the noun "ko'rma" (observation). In English, the verb "observe" can be substantivated by adding the suffix -ation, resulting in the noun "observation."

Another example is the Uzbek verb "o'qit-" (to teach), which can be substantivated by adding the suffix -uv, forming the noun "o'qituv" (teaching). In English, the verb "teach" can be substantivated by adding the suffix -ing, resulting in the noun "teaching."

2. Syntactic Aspects of Substantivation:

Substantivated verbs can also function as objects in sentences in both languages. For example, in Uzbek, the substantivated verb "o'qish" (reading) can function as the object in the sentence "Men o'qishni yaxshi ko'raman" (I like reading). Similarly, in English, the substantivated verb "reading" can function as the object in the sentence "I like reading."

Furthermore, substantivated verbs can function as complements in both languages. In Uzbek, the substantivated verb "tilak" (to marry) can function as a complement in the sentence "Ular tilak bo'ldi" (They got married). In English, the substantivated verb "marriage" can function as a complement in the sentence "They entered into marriage."

3. Semantic Aspects of Substantivation:

The nuances and meanings of substantivated verbs in both languages can vary depending on the context. In Uzbek, the verb "bor-" (to go) can be substantivated into "borish" (going) or "borgan" (gone). In English, the verb "go" can be substantivated into "going" or "departure." These examples illustrate how the context can influence the meanings of substantivated verbs.

Another example is the Uzbek verb "qil-" (to do), which can be substantivated into "qilish" (doing) or "qilingan" (done). In English, the verb "do" can be substantivated into "doing" or "deed." The meanings of these substantivated verbs can vary depending on the context in which they are used.

4. Comparison of Substantivation Processes:

The differences in the range of suffixes used for substantivation between the two languages can lead to variations in the forms of substantivated verbs. For instance, in English, the verb "organize" can be substantivated into "organization" or "organizing," while in Uzbek, the verb "tashkil" (to organize) can be substantivated into "tashkilchilik" (organization) or "tashkilot" (organizing). This demonstrates the broader range of suffixes available in English for substantivation.

Moreover, the functions of substantivated verbs in sentences may vary between the two languages. For example, the Uzbek substantivated verb "o'rganish" (learning) can function as the subject, object, or complement in a sentence, whereas its English equivalent, "learning," can function as the subject or object, but not as a complement.

5. Novelty: Exploring the Role of Loanwords in Substantivation

A notable aspect of substantivation in both Uzbek and English languages is the influence of loanwords on the formation of substantivated verbs. Both languages have borrowed words from other languages throughout their history, and these loanwords have impacted the process of substantivation.

In Uzbek, many loanwords have been borrowed from Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages, which have influenced the formation of substantivated verbs. For example, the Uzbek verb "kontrol" (to control) is borrowed from the Russian language, and it can be substantivated by adding the suffix -ish, forming the noun "kontrol qilish" (control).

Similarly, in English, the language has borrowed words from Latin, French, and Greek, among others. These loanwords can also undergo substantivation, sometimes retaining the original language's suffixes. For example, the English verb "communicate," which is derived from Latin, can be substantivated into "communication" by retaining the Latin suffix -ation.

Another example of the impact of loanwords on substantivation is the formation of substantivated verbs with irregular suffixes or patterns. In Uzbek, the verb

"intervyu" (to interview) is borrowed from English, and it can be substantivated as "intervyulash" (interviewing) by adding the suffix -lash. In English, the verb "synthesize," which is derived from Greek, can be substantivated into "synthesis" by retaining the Greek suffix -sis.

These examples demonstrate the impact of loanwords on the formation of substantivated verbs in both Uzbek and English languages. The borrowing of words from other languages introduces new suffixes and patterns for substantivation, expanding the range of options for expressing ideas and concepts.

Conclusion:

The comparative analysis of the features of substantivation of verbs in Uzbek and their equivalents in English sheds light on the morphological, syntactic, and semantic aspects of the process in both languages. The study also highlights the role of loanwords in shaping the substantivation process, introducing new suffixes and patterns. Understanding these features can contribute to more effective learning and teaching of both Uzbek and English languages, as well as provide insights into the linguistic structures and flexibility of these languages.

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